

Reproduction of "Measuring Item Global Residual Value for Fair Recommendation"

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This reproducibility paper aims to reproduce the results from the paper "Measuring Item Global Residual Value for Fair Recommendation"[8]. The authors propose a new framework for fair recommendation focused on time, which is linked to a Github repository[7]. In our attempt to reproduce the results, we encountered several challenges. While the code was available, it was not functional out of the box and lacked any documentation. Pre-processing steps, hyperparameter choices and dependencies were unspecified, making it difficult to replicate the findings. Parts of the data preparation pipeline were missing, which had to be reverse engineered. Our findings highlight the importance of thorough documentation and dataset accessibility, to ensure reproducibility in machine learning research.

CCS Concepts: • **Information systems** → **Recommender systems**.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Reproducibility paper, Recommendation system, Item Fairness, Timeliness Distribution

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1 Introduction

Recommender systems play an important role in digital platforms, by providing personalized content based on user behavior [9]. However, these systems often suffer from popularity biases, where well-known items are favored, while exposure for new or less popular content is limited. This imbalance creates a feedback loop, known as the snowball effect, where widely recommended items continue to dominate, while others struggle to gain visibility [8].

To solve this problem, the paper "Measuring Item Global Residual Value for Fair Recommendation" introduces a new method to measure how long an item remains important [8]. This measurement is called Global Residual Value (GRV) and it uses ideas from survival analysis. With GRV, the authors propose the Timeliness-aware Fair Recommendation (TaFR) framework. This framework tries to balance fairness and accuracy in recommendations.

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Reproducibility is a crucial part of scientific research and enables verifying findings independently. Our goal in this study is to reproduce the results of the paper and document the necessary steps taken to reach this goal or the missing details that made a reproduction impossible.

2 Experimental setup

2.1 Datasets

The official paper mentions using two datasets, namely the Microsoft News Dataset (MIND) dataset and the Kuai dataset [8].

Since no links were provided towards downloading the datasets neither in the paper nor in the Github repository, it was our task to find these datasets. For the MIND dataset, this was quickly achieved, since a website was created only to introduce and download the dataset additionally to the according paper¹. The MIND dataset was collected from anonymized behavior logs of Microsoft News website.

The Kuai dataset was more difficult to find. This is due to the fact that there exist three Kuai datasets, the KuaiRec², the KuaiRand and the KuaiSAR. The paper never mentions the specific Kuai dataset, but relies only on the general description, the Kuai dataset. Therefore, we assumed the KuaiRec dataset to be the most suitable even though all three datasets are aimed to be trained on recommender models. This assumption was finally approved once another user raised a Github issue mentioning the KuaiRec dataset [6].

From there on, two more datasets were needed to run the code, namely *cox.csv* and *itemHourLog.csv*. Here, the Github issue helped with the missing information on how to create the first dataset, the cox dataset. Since there was still no documentation provided on the second dataset, the itemHourLog dataset, we published a comment and received a reply within a few days. Unfortunately, no sample data was provided but instead a description of both datasets. "To clarify, ItemHourLog.csv contains information about the item based on the interaction log, while cox.csv includes the Cox model predictions, which provide the probability of the item's survival at each moment." [6] Due to this lack of information, we created a Jupyter notebook to reengineer both of these datasets. The notebook is stored as *createDatasets.ipynb* and can be found in our repository inside the data folder.

For the whole project we used a subset of the MIND dataset. Concluding this chapter, we have to assume that the reproduced datasets differ to the ones used in TaFR [8].

2.2 Platform

For the project we used Python as a programming language with the version 3.12.3, along with Jupyter notebooks. The original repository [7] did not provide any information about requirements, which is why we created a *requirements.txt* with the necessary packages. The experiments were run locally on two different operating systems, Windows 11 and Ubuntu 24.04.

3 Approaches and Implementation

It was a challenging task to reproduce the required datasets for the given project, but to optimize the code in a manner to be executable and stay as tight to the original solution as possible was just as difficult. How we reached the point to be able to execute the original project is explained in the following chapter.

¹<https://msnews.github.io/>

²<https://kuaiREC.com/>

3.1 Reproducing Backbone results

Since the paper provided several results from models used as baselines and stated from the paper as "backbone results" [8], we aimed to reproduce these results. Although, our main focus was to reproduce the results from the TaFR framework.

Due to time constraints we were not able trying the third backbone model, the TiSASRec.

3.1.1 NeuMF - Neural Matrix Factorization.

NeuMF [2] is the implementation of the Neural Collaborative Filtering (NCF) paper [1]. NCF is a collaborative filtering approach that is used in recommendation systems. It improves traditional methods such as Matrix Factorization (MF) by using neural networks to capture complex user-item interactions.

NeuMF - original Our first approach to reproduce the backbone results was to use the original code as it was also referenced in the TaFR paper. Unfortunately, the repository has not been updated since 2018. Therefore, the versions of the libraries used were outdated and the code did not run out of the box. The same problems applied to the Dockerfile where the provided configuration did not work. After some hours of debugging, we decided to look for alternative options.

NeuMF - Pytorch We found another GitHub repository [10] that had the NeuMF model implemented in Pytorch. The code ran out of the box with the provided *movielens* dataset. The code contained a few lines to preprocess the dataset for the following model training. We created our own function to preprocess the MIND dataset to create the required structure. Unfortunately, simply swapping out the dataset was not enough to train the model for MIND. At this point, we decided not to continue further with recreating the "backbone" results for NeuMF.

3.1.2 GRU4Rec- Session-Based Recommendations with RNNs.

GRU4Rec is a session-based recommender system using Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) to model user interactions within short sessions. It was introduced by Hidasi et al. [3] to improve on traditional MF methods. These older methods work well on long-term user data, but struggle with short-term sessions.

GRU4Rec - Original Implementation

The original GitHub repository [4] released with the paper uses Theano for model training. However, we encountered challenges due to deprecated dependencies (Theano 0.7) and compatibility issues with modern Python environments. After multiple unsuccessful attempts to find workarounds, we switched to the pytorch-reimplementation.

GRU4Rec - PyTorch Reimplementation

We successfully utilized the PyTorch reimplementation from [5], which recreates GRU4Rec while replacing the original Theano framework with PyTorch. While the Theano implementation [4] provides slightly faster training times due to its low-level optimizations, the PyTorch version offers significantly easier reproducibility, because of its compatibility with current Python ecosystems. Differences in efficiency of the 3 implementations (Theano, PyTorch, Tensorflow) are further analyzed in the repository's README documentation, including benchmark comparisons and hardware requirements.

We were able to successfully reproduce the results of the GRU4Rec PyTorch reimplementation on the RSC15 dataset³. The model was trained for 10 epochs on a NVIDIA GTX 970, with a total

³<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/chadgostopp/recsys-challenge-2015>

training time of approximately 5 hours. The obtained recall and Mean Reciprocal Rank (MRR) metrics are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Reproducibility Results on RSC15 Dataset

Dataset	Recall@1	Recall@5	Recall@10	Recall@20	MRR@1	MRR@5	MRR@10	MRR@20
Our Results	0.1659	0.4697	0.6065	0.7161	0.1659	0.2765	0.2948	0.3026
GitHub Repo	0.1829	0.4478	0.5715	0.6789	0.1829	0.2783	0.2949	0.3024

The reproduced results show high agreement with the repository values, with small variations likely due to differences in hardware, software versions, or random initialization.

As a next step, reproducing the backbone implementation results from [8] would require preprocessing of the MIND dataset and training the model. However, this poses a challenge, as neither the paper nor its repository clearly specify the preprocessing steps or hyperparameters used.

3.2 Reproducing TaFR results

To highlight the challenges encountered attempting to execute the code from the GitHub repository, we first reviewed the different arguments. The `main.py` file can be launched with several arguments to set parameters, such as selecting the model or specifying the data source. While many arguments are self-explanatory, some can cause confusion. The authors provide a shell script, `run.sh`, which features a sample execution with multiple parameters.

Key Parameters

A brief description of the three key arguments is given in the `help` function:

- **load:** "Load a pre-trained model or not."
- **train:** "Train the model or not."
- **analysis:** "Analyze prediction results."

Argument: load Setting `load` to 0 prevents the program from loading a saved model. When set to 1, it attempts to load the model specified by the `model_path` parameter, which is useful for reusing existing models. If the specified model does not exist, the program crashes. Unfortunately, the original authors did not provide any pre-trained models, and since `run.sh` uses `load=1`, executing the script results in a crash.

Argument: train Running the program with `train=1` initiates model training and saves the results in a file specified by `model_path`, typically in `.h5` format. Using `load=1` and `train=1` simultaneously will overwrite the existing model.

Argument: analysis This argument determines whether the `model.analysis()` function is called to produce prediction result insights. In the provided `run.sh`, this argument is not set, and thus the function is not executed.

Setting this argument led to several issues. For example, `itemInfo` is created without including `timelevel`, which causes an error during aggregation.

We resolved this by including `timelevel` in the aggregation. We also had to rework the usages of the `getRank` function by resetting the index.

Results Applying these fixes and implementing our dataset transformation yielded the following analysis results:

```

1 # Group 0 SA_group
2 0.8916256157635468 362 406
3 # Group 0 base_group
4 0.07635467980295567 31 406

```

Listing 1. Sample Analysis Results

We found no documentation for these outputs. Based on code analysis, we infer that the first print refers to the `SA_group` and the second to `base_group`. The first column seems to represent the ratio of the sizes of the whole group and the subgroup of rows having `per_ranks` smaller than 0.1.

Due to limited resources and missing documentation, we were unable to fully interpret these results or understand the rationale behind the chosen metrics.

We also were able to create an output graph Fig: 1. Unfortunately, we were not able to find this graph in the paper and therefore could not verify the results. Also it remains unclear what the graph is supposed to explain.

Fig. 1. Output Graph

4 Challenges

During the whole project several challenges were faced. Since the repository was neither running out of the box nor was it documented with a profounding *README.md*, the challenge to reproduce the results of the paper started within the first attempt. For clarity, we decided to provide a table describing all the challenges faced in Table 2. On the other side, this table can also be seen as the required improvements to be done by the authors of the paper to enable reproducibility of their paper.

The challenges described in Table 2 were separated into three parts, the data set, the code and the overall reproducibility process. Another challenge was to divide the amount of work to each group member. In the end Tobias Kutscher and Leon Beccard were mainly responsible for executing the TaFR framework, where Kutscher wrote chapter 3.2. Alexander Posztos was responsible for reproducing the GRU4Rec implementation and its chapter 3.1.2. Leon Rischar on the side produced the content for chapter 3.1.1. Adeel Ahmad was responsible for the first chapter with the help of others. The chapters 2, 4 and 5 were written by Leon Beccard.

5 Conclusion

Concerns are raised about the consistency and reliability of the results, because of the inability to reproduce the papers results due to missing subsets and executable code. The repository of the paper might still be active with a replying author. Due to the answers in the Github Issue [6] though, it seems quite clear that this project has been finished and will not be optimized with improved documentation.

With satisfaction we can look back to the accomplishment to do the necessary changes on the code

A. Data	
1. Datasets available	Yes
2. Subsets used in project available	No
3. Documentation on creation of subsets available	No
4. Metadata available	No
5. Data description available	No
6. Data description partially available	Yes
B. Code	
1. Code available	Yes
2. Code running out of the box	No
3. Code documentation provided	No
4. Code setup requirements provided	No
5. Code needs several fixes to be executable	Yes
C. Reproducibility process	
1. Comparison of results of paper possible	No
2. Code outputting graphs similar to graphs in paper	No

Table 2. Summary of challenges

to make it executable and receive some output. Thereby, we can state that almost the whole range of possibilities to reproduce the papers has been exhausted except for reproducing the results of the backbone model *TiSASRec*. This missing model only serves for comparison though and is not of high interest since the proposed new TaFR framework has been the main focus of this paper. Therefore, this has been our main focus too and we can conclude that the whole setup disables researchers to use the TaFR[7] framework in a meaningful way.

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